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I say to them tonight, there's not a liberal America and a conservative America – there's the United States of America."

In this excerpt, Obama repeats the phrase "there's" to emphasize his point about the importance of unity and the rejection of divisive politics.

2008 Election Victory Speech:

"It's the answer that led those who've been told for so long by so many to be cynical and fearful and doubtful about what we can achieve to put their hands on the arc of history and bend it once more toward the hope of a better day."

Here, Obama uses the phrase "it's the" to highlight the transformative power of hope and inspire his audience to work towards a brighter future.

2015 Selma Commemoration Speech:

"We are the people Langston Hughes wrote of, who 'build our temples for tomorrow, strong as we know how.' We are the people Emerson wrote of, 'who for truth and honor's sake stand fast and suffer long.' We are the people who do not believe that freedom is reserved for the lucky or happiness for the few."

In this excerpt, Obama repeats the phrase "We are the people" to emphasize the collective power and responsibility of the American citizens in shaping the nation's future.

These examples demonstrate how Barack Obama effectively utilized anaphora in his speeches to convey his messages with impact, rhythm, and emphasis, leaving a lasting impression on his listeners.

Epiphora: This is the opposite of anaphora, where a word or phrase is repeated at the end of successive clauses or sentences. Obama used epiphora to drive home his points and create a memorable impact. In his 2008 victory speech, he said, "It's the

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answer spoken by Americans who sent a message to the world that we have never been a collection of Red States and Blue States: we are, and always will be, the United States of America."

In his 2008 victory speech in Grant Park, Chicago, after winning the presidential election, Obama used epiphora to reinforce his message of hope and unity. He frequently repeated the phrase "Yes, we can," which became a prominent slogan of his campaign. Here is an excerpt from that speech:

"It's been a long time coming, but tonight, because of what we did on this day, in this election, at this defining moment, change has come to America. I congratulate Governor Palin for all that they've achieved. And I look forward to working with them to renew this nation's promise in the months ahead. To my sister Maya, my sister Auma, all my other brothers and sisters, thank you so much for all the support that you've given me. But above all, I will never forget who this victory truly belongs to. It belongs to you. It belongs to you."

In this excerpt, one can see how Obama repeats the phrase "I congratulate" when acknowledging Senator McCain and Governor Palin. Additionally, he repeats the phrase "the love of my life" when referring to Michelle Obama. These repetitions create a powerful and rhythmic effect, reinforcing his message of unity, gratitude, and acknowledgment.

Conducipatio: This involves repeating a key word from a preceding phrase or clause in the following one. Obama used this technique to reinforce his message and highlight important ideas. In his 2013 inaugural address, he stated, "*We, the people, declare today that the most evident of truths -- that all of us are created equal -- is the star that guides us still; just as it guided our forebears through*

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where you come from, what you look like, or who you love. But if you don't, you'll fall behind, no matter what you look like or where you come from or who you love."

"The question we ask today is not whether our government is too big or too small, but whether it works - whether it helps families find jobs at a decent wage, care they can afford when they get sick, a retirement that is dignified."

"Change will not come if we wait for some other person or some other time. We are the ones we've been waiting for. We are the change that we seek."

These are just a few examples of the types of repetition Obama utilized in his speeches. By skillfully employing repetition, he was able to enhance the impact and persuasiveness of his messages, making them more memorable and engaging for his audience.

Conclusion:

It is important to note that the ethical implications of repetition in political contexts can vary significantly between authoritarian regimes and democratic societies. In authoritarian contexts, repetition is often used to consolidate power and restrict freedoms, whereas in democratic societies, it should ideally serve as a means to inform, persuade, and engage citizens in an open and accountable political system. The analyses show that, the strategic use of repetition in Barack Obama's speeches enhance rhetorical power, engages the audience, and reinforces the central

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message. He emphasizes key ideas, create a rhythmic flow, build anticipation, connect with the audience, and reinforce rhetorical devices. His skilled use of repetition contributed to his reputation as an inspiring and influential public speaker.

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